

FLOSSolitaire

Detlef Burkhardt

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15500894

Inhaltsverzeichnis

- 1 FLOSSolitaire Card Games 3**
 - 1.1 Colophon 3
 - 1.2 Introduction 4
 - 1.3 Call to Action 4

- 2 Evaluation Criteria 5**

- 3 Requirements Catalog 6**
 - 3.1 Basic Requirements (Must-Haves) 6
 - 3.2 Game Mechanics & Logic 6
 - 3.3 UI & Design 6
 - 3.4 Architecture & Maintainability 7
 - 3.5 Extensibility (Optional/Advanced) 7
 - 3.6 Maturity Rating (Scale) 7

- 4 Web-based FLOSS Solitaire Projects – Maturity Table 8**

- 5 Unity Solitaire Projects 9**

- 6 Godot Solitaire Projects for Inspiration 10**

1 FLOSSolitaire Card Games

1.1 Colophon

Description:

Collection of some Free/Libre Open Source Projects around Solitaire and Cardgames

Tags:

CardGame Game Solitaire GameDev OpenSource IndieDev

Type: Working Paper

license: CC-BY-SA 4.0

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15512244 (Version)
10.5281/zenodo.15511992 (Concept)

version: 0.7.6

date: 2025-04-29

last: 2025-05-25

contact: info[@]fosseam.org

Author: Detlef Burkhardt <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9155-716X>

DOI-Link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15511992>

1.2 Introduction

... to learn, to play, to compare, to create & build a better one.

This collection brings together open-source solitaire games based on different technologies. The goal of this collection is not only to study classic card logic or analyze creative game mechanics, but above all to get to know different modern frameworks in direct comparison and to apply them in practice.

In addition to web frameworks, we also look at solutions created with game engines.

On the web, this curated list covers a wide range of technological paradigms, from React and Vue.js to Svelte, Vanilla JavaScript, and Flutter. The selected projects are perfect for developers who:

- want to learn about differences in component architecture and state management,
- want to become familiar with drag-and-drop mechanics, animations, and game state management,
- or want to develop their own forks or variants of a solitaire game – whether for learning, UI/UX tests, or creative extensions.

A special focus is on diversity: each project brings its own solutions, technological features, and community standards, providing high educational value for the practical study of web technologies.

This collection can serve both as a source of inspiration and as a testing ground for framework decisions, refactoring exercises, or UI prototyping.

1.3 Call to Action

So let's analyse the first 3-4 Projects per Group together.

You can reach me via LinkedIn, Bluesky, Mastodon or via email info@fosseam.org.

Perhaps after this, we build the best FLOSS Solitaire ever seen^^.

2 Evaluation Criteria

Criterion	Description
UX & Gameplay	How smooth and intuitive is the gameplay? Is the user guidance clear, the layout clear, the interaction pleasant?
Code Quality	Is the source code structured, understandable, documented? Are modern patterns used (e.g., hooks, stores, modularization)?
Learning Potential	How well is the project suited for understanding the concepts of the respective framework? Is it a template, entry point, or reference?
Simplicity	How quickly can the project be set up, understood, and extended locally?
Extensibility	Is the architecture open enough to add e.g. game rules, UI themes, or modes?
Drag & Drop Implementation	Is a framework (e.g. React-DnD) used or a custom solution? Is the implementation stable and understandable?
Responsiveness & Mobile	Can the game be played well on tablets and smartphones? Is the layout responsive?
Build & Toolchain	How complex or simple is the build system? For example, is there Vite, Webpack, or no build needed?
Framework Maturity	Is the framework stable and well documented (e.g., Vue 3 vs. experimental setup)?
Suitability as Template	How well is the project suited as a basis for a web component implementation? Evaluation includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none">→ Modularity & component structure→ Separation of logic and presentation→ Use of modern web standards (e.g., Shadow DOM)→ Clean code & maintainability→ Documentation & community support

3 Requirements Catalog

The idea: to develop a solitaire system based on web components. Here is an overview of possible requirements.

3.1 Basic Requirements (Must-Haves)

Area	Requirements
Component Technology Modularization	Use of native web components (custom elements, Shadow DOM, HTML templates), ideally with Lit or Stencil
Framework Independence	Each UI unit as its own component: e.g. <code><sol-card></code> , <code><sol-stack></code> , <code><sol-game></code>
Accessibility (a11y)	Components must run without React, Vue, Angular, etc.
Build & Deploy	Basic ARIA roles, keyboard control possible
	Simple setup with Vite or Rollup, optionally usable as PWA

3.2 Game Mechanics & Logic

Area	Requirements
Card Deck	Complete deck, shuffling, drag & drop behavior
Move Rules	Rule-compliant placement on foundation, tableau logic
Undo / Restart	At least basic undo and restart function
Win Condition	Detection, animation, optionally auto-win
One-Click Function	Cards that can be placed without ambiguity are automatically moved by a simple click

3.3 UI & Design

Area	Requirements
Responsive Design	Functional on desktop, tablet, mobile
Scalability	Cards scale with screen size, grid layout
Themeability	Simple customization via CSS custom properties or slots
Animations	Smooth movements for drag, card moves, win animation

3.4 Architecture & Maintainability

Area	Requirements
Separation of Logic & Presentation	Logic in JS classes or services, presentation via slots or templates
Testability	Components with unit tests (e.g., Playwright, Web Test Runner)
Readability & Clean Code	Clear structure, no global states, reusability
Documentation	README, dev demo, possibly Storybook integration

3.5 Extensibility (Optional/Advanced)

Area	Requirements
Additional Game Modes	Spider, Freecell, Pyramid, etc. in later modules
Statistics / Score	Points, move count, time (optionally switchable off)
PWA Function	Playable offline, installable (add to homescreen)
Barrier-free Version	Contrast mode, keyboard operation, reduced animations

3.6 Maturity Rating (Scale)

Maturity	Meaning
Top	Active development, good structure, many features, community signals
Good	Solid architecture, useful for starter projects, moderate activity
Average	Functional or technically interesting, but little maintained or rough
Low	Prototypical, test repo, little community or further development

4 Web-based FLOSS Solitaire Projects – Maturity Table

Nr.	Name / Project	Maturity	Tech Stack	Platform	License	Special Feature / Recommendation
1	drtobal/solitaire	Top	Angular 17	Web	MIT	Modern UI, drag & drop, undo, auto-solve
2	dnotes/solitairetable	Top	SvelteKit + Tailwind	Web (PWA)	MIT	Supports variants, configurable, offline-capable
3	AadumKhor/Solitaire_Flutter	Top	Dart + Flutter	Web, Android, iOS, Desktop	MIT	Cross-platform, modern UI, app-ready
4	hicaku/solitaire	Good	Vue.js 3 + Tailwind	Web	MIT	Modern structure, composition API
5	silent-lad/VueSolitaire	Good	Vue.js 2	Web	MIT	Multiple modes (Klondike, Spider), native DnD
6	gcedo/react-solitaire	Good	React + Redux	Web	MIT	Drag & drop with React DnD
7	pharrington/Solitairey	Good	Vanilla JS	Web	MIT	Minimal, no build system needed
8	foss-card-games/Solitairey	Good	Vanilla JS	Web	MIT	Well-maintained fork, structured design
9	devatrox/Solitaire	Average	React + TypeScript	Web	MIT	Compact, ideal entry into TS
10	pl12133/react-solitaire	Average	React + Redux	Web	MIT	Undo/redo, mobile-ready, classic structure
11	Hobbytowo/spider-solitaire-game	Average	Vue.js 2.5	Web	MIT	Focus on Spider variant, nice UI
12	janne/freecell-svelte	Average	Svelte + TypeScript	Web (PWA)	MIT	Freecell PWA with clear structure
13	pinndulum/ngCardGames	Average	Angular 15	Web	MIT	Modular design, card game framework
14	msaf94/svelte-solitaire	Low	Svelte + TypeScript	Web	MIT	Minimal structure, ideal for Svelte beginners
15	ankurrsinghal/svelte-solitaire	Low	Svelte + TS + Tailwind	Web	MIT	WIP, good foundation for game system logic

5 Unity Solitaire Projects

Nr.	Name	Maturity	Short Info
1	gubicsz/Solitaire	Top	Full-featured, modern Klondike with MVP, Zenject, UniRx; many commits
2	Nichathans-Solitaire-Pack	Good	Collection of 6 solitaire variants, independent code, smaller community
3	jakedowns/Solitaire3D	Good	3D variant for mobile devices, fork of gubicsz, kept up to date
4	BenjaminHamon/Solitaire	Average	Simple Unity project, structured, but low activity
5	ksharma67/Classic-Solitaire-Unity	Average	Few metadata, probably rudimentary, but visually ambitious
6	DSA/solitaire-game	Average	Stack/queue approach, young project, but with structural idea
7	Dans1997/Unity-Classic-Solitaire	Low	Single developer, no forks or releases, probably hackathon project
8	Juvar Abrera / solitaire-game	Low	Only one commit, no README, pure test project

6 Godot Solitaire Projects for Inspiration

Nr.	Name	Maturity	Godot Version	Short Description
1	godot-freecell	Top	Godot 3.x	Fully playable FreeCell with clear structure and free assets
2	Solitaire (Ron-Scottznbrgr)	Top	Godot 4.0	Extensive with setup instructions, C# integration
3	Godot_Solitaire	Good	Godot 3.x	Drag-and-drop with auto-move (right-click), compiled for multiple platforms
4	Solitaire-Godot4	Good	Godot 4.x	Solid tutorial with drag-and-drop and basic logic, ideal for beginners
5	Veneno	Good	Godot 4	Card game demo with AI integration
6	godotSolitaire	Average	Godot 3.x	Basic game with simple stack and game structure
7	card-framework	Average	Godot 3.x/4.x	Framework for card games, not solitaire directly, but very usable
8	Salaenor/Solitaire	Low	Godot 3.x	Simple structure, focus on editor integration
9	GabeContra/GodotSolitaire	Low	Unknown	Unfinished learning project, provides good insights into basic structure
10	w-dib/Solitaire	Low	Godot 4.4	Experimental design with a learning focus